

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Chloronitrobenzenes by Some uni- and poly-Valent Cations and Anions vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

SARNAM SINGH SHAKYA, KAILASH CHANDRA and MUKHTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Agra College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 26 March 1982, revised 21 January 1983, accepted 23 April 1983

The suppression of the polarographic negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes in borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.09 has been attempted at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using some uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, viz., Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and I^- , CNS^- , oxalate $^{2-}$, citrate $^{3-}$, as suppressors. The electrode reactions of the depolarizers have been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in the presence of different amounts of these suppressors. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) have been calculated by Koutecky's method. Efficacies of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions in the suppression of the negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes have been determined on the basis of αn_a values. A tentative mechanism for the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes at pH 7.09 has also been postulated. The ease of reduction of three isomers at dme follows the order *meta* > *ortho* > *para*.

In continuation of our earlier publication¹ on the effect of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes, we report in this paper the results of our investigations on the suppression of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes by some uni- and poly-valent cations and anions vis-a-vis their effect on the kinetics of the electrode reaction.

Experimental

Experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹. The number of electrons, n , involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon². This gave the value of n equal to 4 for each depolarizer at pH 7.09. Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of the diffusion coefficient, D , of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes at various concentrations of the suppressive ions. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{f,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky's method^{3,4}. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs E_{de} . Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e. the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁵⁽⁶⁾. The following uni- and poly-valent cations and anions were used: cations (nitrate being the anion in each case) Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} ; anions (potassium being the cation in each case) CNS^- , I^- , oxalate $^{2-}$ and citrate $^{3-}$. The dme had the following capillary characteristics: (a) for *o*-chloronitrobenzene: $m = 2.77$ mg/sec;

$t = 2.92$ sec; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.358$ mg $^{2/3}$ sec $^{-1/6}$ (in 0.1 M NaNO_3 , open circuit), $h_{corr} = 56.2$ cm. (b) for *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes: $m = 1.498$ mg/sec, $t = 2.75$ sec, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.759$ mg $^{2/3}$ sec $^{-1/6}$ (in 0.1 M NaNO_3 , open circuit), $h_{corr} = 56.2$ cm.

Results and Discussion

Polarity of the maxima :

The first kind polarographic maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes in borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.09 for a given concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of each depolarizer and at the same height of the mercury column ($h_{corr} = 56.2$ cm) appear at -0.68 , -0.62 and -0.72 V (vs SCE), respectively. These lie well on the negative side of the potential of the electro-capillary zero which is -0.32 V (vs SCE) under the same experimental conditions. Since $E_{1/2}$ values of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes at pH 7.09 also lie on the negative side of the electro-capillary zero, the maxima of these depolarizers are of negative polarity⁶. The relative heights of the maxima are in the order *m*-chloronitrobenzene > *o*-chloronitrobenzene > *p*-chloronitrobenzene.

Effect of increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions on the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes :

The effect of increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations (Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+}) and anions (I^- , CNS^- , oxalate $^{2-}$ and citrate $^{3-}$) on the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes has been studied and the values of E_{max} and i_{max} have been presented in Table 1. It is seen that with the

TABLE I—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-CHLORONITROBENZENES IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLY-VALENT CATIONS AND ANIONS

[Depolarizer] = 1.0×10^{-3} M ; [NaNO₃] = 0.1 M ; pH (borax-boric acid buffer) = 7.09 ; temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

[Ion] (M)	-E _{max} V (SCE)	-E _{1/2} V (SCE)	i _{max} (μA)	i _d (μA)	slope (mV)	D × 10 ⁶ (cm ² /sec)	α _{Na}	k _p ⁰ (cm/sec)
<i>o</i> -Chloronitrobenzene (in 4% ethanolic solution)								
0.0	0.68	—	38.40	—	—	—	—	—
Na ⁺								
4.75	0.60	—	15.68	—	—	—	—	—
*5.00	—	0.385	—	15.36	65	5.32	0.849	5.31×10^{-5}
5.50	—	0.380	—	15.04	63	5.10	0.862	7.48×10^{-5}
Ca ²⁺								
2.00	0.54	—	16.32	—	—	—	—	—
*2.16	—	0.416	—	15.68	63	5.54	0.869	7.02×10^{-5}
3.00	—	0.395	—	13.12	61	3.88	0.894	8.09×10^{-5}
Al ³⁺ × 10								
0.15	0.50	—	22.09	—	—	—	—	—
*0.16	—	0.310	—	21.76	61	10.68	0.899	8.31×10^{-5}
5.00	—	0.900	—	20.48	60	9.46	0.906	1.07×10^{-4}
I ⁻								
0.75	0.62	—	21.12	—	—	—	—	—
*0.80	—	0.420	—	20.80	62	9.75	0.922	5.37×10^{-5}
1.50	—	0.400	—	19.62	61	8.59	0.939	6.48×10^{-5}
CNS ⁻								
0.98	0.58	—	20.16	—	—	—	—	—
0.40	—	0.425	—	19.84	63	8.88	0.963	6.40×10^{-5}
1.00	—	0.415	—	20.48	62	9.46	0.981	9.01×10^{-5}
Oxalate ²⁻								
1.50	0.62	—	19.84	—	—	—	—	—
*1.65	—	0.425	—	16.54	62	6.24	0.876	2.97×10^{-5}
1.75	—	0.410	—	13.44	61	4.07	0.898	4.31×10^{-5}
Citrate ³⁻								
1.40	0.62	—	17.28	—	—	—	—	—
*1.50	—	0.490	—	16.96	61	6.48	0.899	3.41×10^{-5}
1.75	—	0.420	—	16.00	59	5.77	0.916	5.10×10^{-5}
<i>m</i> -Chloronitrobenzene (in 4% ethanolic solution)								
0.0	0.62	—	40.00	—	—	—	—	—
Na ⁺								
4.00	0.55	—	16.96	—	—	—	—	—
*4.50	—	0.385	—	15.04	57	9.16	0.943	6.80×10^{-5}
5.00	—	0.392	—	14.72	56	8.78	0.961	8.10×10^{-5}
Ca ²⁺								
1.90	0.42	—	13.76	—	—	—	—	—
*2.00	—	0.345	—	13.44	57	7.32	0.950	8.85×10^{-5}
3.00	—	0.320	—	11.31	56	4.76	0.967	9.90×10^{-5}
Al ³⁺								
0.10	0.33	—	16.96	—	—	—	—	—
*0.12	—	0.320	—	15.60	56	9.96	0.972	9.41×10^{-5}
0.50	—	0.289	—	14.72	55	8.78	0.985	1.05×10^{-4}
I ⁻								
0.90	0.56	—	15.68	—	—	—	—	—
*1.00	—	0.400	—	15.36	68	9.56	0.384	6.32×10^{-5}
1.50	—	0.390	—	14.72	65	8.78	0.867	8.48×10^{-5}
CNS ⁻								
0.57	0.56	—	16.32	—	—	—	—	—
*0.60	—	0.405	—	15.36	68	9.56	0.898	8.31×10^{-5}
1.20	—	0.400	—	15.68	66	9.96	0.921	8.82×10^{-5}
Oxalate ²⁻								
1.40	0.54	—	15.36	—	—	—	—	—
*1.50	—	0.400	—	15.04	67	9.16	0.809	4.63×10^{-5}
1.70	—	0.395	—	14.72	66	8.78	0.819	6.01×10^{-5}
Citrate ³⁻								
1.25	0.57	—	16.96	—	—	—	—	—
*1.40	—	0.400	—	14.08	66	8.08	0.821	5.62×10^{-5}
1.75	—	0.390	—	13.44	65	7.32	0.889	7.81×10^{-5}

(Table 1 Contd.)

p-Chloronitrobenzene (in 25% ethanolic solution)								
0.0	0.72	—	33.60	—	—	—	—	—
Na ⁺								
4.50	0.64	—	17.28	—	—	—	—	—
*5.00	—	0.425	—	15.36	62	9.56	0.893	1.31 × 10 ⁻⁵
5.28	—	0.415	—	14.72	60	8.78	0.901	3.29 × 10 ⁻⁵
Ca ⁺⁺								
2.75	0.50	—	15.36	—	—	—	—	—
*3.00	—	0.420	—	14.72	61	8.78	0.909	4.32 × 10 ⁻⁵
3.25	—	0.410	—	14.08	57	8.03	0.932	6.39 × 10 ⁻⁵
Al ⁺⁺								
0.10	0.36	—	15.68	—	—	—	—	—
*0.14	—	0.370	—	14.08	60	8.03	0.912	8.05 × 10 ⁻⁵
0.40	—	0.340	—	14.72	59	8.78	0.924	1.50 × 10 ⁻⁴
I ⁻								
1.40	0.60	—	15.68	—	—	—	—	—
*1.50	—	0.430	—	15.36	60	9.56	0.893	2.66 × 10 ⁻⁵
2.00	—	0.420	—	14.40	59	8.40	0.901	5.92 × 10 ⁻⁵
CNS ⁻								
0.15	0.64	—	17.28	—	—	—	—	—
*0.18	—	0.425	—	14.08	59	8.03	0.911	3.68 × 10 ⁻⁵
0.88	—	0.380	—	15.36	58	9.56	0.932	4.84 × 10 ⁻⁵
Oxalate ²⁻								
1.00	0.66	—	18.88	—	—	—	—	—
*1.25	—	0.435	—	15.36	69	9.56	0.782	1.61 × 10 ⁻⁵
1.35	—	0.420	—	14.72	68	8.78	0.789	2.86 × 10 ⁻⁵
Citrate ³⁻								
1.00	0.61	—	17.92	—	—	—	—	—
*1.20	—	0.430	—	15.36	69	9.56	0.788	1.93 × 10 ⁻⁵
1.40	—	0.422	—	14.72	68	8.78	0.792	3.91 × 10 ⁻⁵

* Concentration at which the maximum gets just suppressed.

addition of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, the value of i_{max} decreases and that of E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials with increasing concentrations of the cations and anions. Singh *et al*⁷ have put forward an explanation for this positive shift in E_{max} .

Diffusion-controlled nature of the polarographic waves of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes :

After the suppression of the maxima by requisite amounts of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes yield, in each case, a well-defined wave at pH 7.09. Millicoulometric studies reveal that the reduction of all the three depolarizers corresponds to a 4-electron reduction process at this pH. The wave-heights are diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the fact that plots of i_d vs $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ are linear and pass through the origin.

Irreversibility of the electrode processes :

Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes in presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions were applied. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a 4-electron reduction

process. It follows from this that the polarographic reduction of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes is irreversible. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{8,9} predicts that current is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the waves and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{corr}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ at different stages of the waves was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{corr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave.

Influence of increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes :

It was found that the values of αn_a and $k_{1,h}^0$ for the electrode reactions of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes tend to increase with increasing concentrations of the uni- and poly-valent cations and anions (Table 1). This shows^{5(c)} that the reduction of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes at dme is rendered increasingly less irreversible with increasing concentrations of the cations and anions. A positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions lends support to

the above conclusion. A comparison of $k_{f,n}^0$ values at the stage where maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes get just suppressed by the uni- and poly-valent cations and anions, may give a quantitative estimation of the influence of these ions on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes. A comparison of $k_{f,n}^0$ values in respect of various uni- and poly-valent cations and anions gives the order $Al^{3+} > Ca^{2+} > Na^+$, and $CNS^- > I^- > citrate^{3-} > oxalate^{2-}$.

Thus, among the uni- and poly-valent cations it is the Al^{3+} that suppresses the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions. The same is true for CNS^- among the anions.

The order of $k_{f,n}^0$ values for the depolarizers at the stage of just suppression of their maxima by uni- and poly-valent cations and anions is *m*-chloronitrobenzene $>$ *o*-chloronitrobenzene $>$ *p*-chloronitrobenzene. Thus, *m*-chloronitrobenzene is easiest to reduce at dme.

Relative efficacies of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions in the suppression of the maxima of o-, m- and p- chloronitrobenzenes on the basis of α_n values :

At the stage where the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes just disappear (marked by an asterisk in Table 1) the order of α_n values signifies⁷ the extent to which the addition of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions renders the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes more irreversible from the position obtaining in absence of these ions. In other words a cation or an anion for which α_n has got a higher value at the point of just suppression of the maxima will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes. On this basis, the following order of relative efficacies of various uni- and poly-valent cations and anions has been established : $Al^{3+} > Ca^{2+} > Na^+$, and $CNS^- > I^- > citrate^{3-} > oxalate^{2-}$.

It is interesting to note that not only uni- and poly-valent cation but also anions suppress the negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes and that their (cations and anions) efficacies follow the valency rule. However, I^- and CNS^- do not follow this generalization. This may be attributed to the fact that both I^- and CNS^- are capillary active substances¹⁰ and as such they should be more effective in suppressing the maxima. Further, the order of efficacies found on the basis of molarity is identical to that obtained on the basis of α_n values.

Mechanism of polarographic reduction of o-, m- and p-chloronitrobenzenes at pH 7.09 :

The 4-electron process of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes represents their reduction to the corresponding phenylhydroxylamine derivatives. Since the plots of $\log k_{f,n}$ vs $E_{d,e}$ in the presence of different uni- and poly-valent cations and anions are linear there is only one rate-determining step^{11,12} involved in the reduction of each depolarizer. The

values of kinetic parameters (α_n and $k_{f,n}^0$) have been calculated at different concentrations of the cations and anions. It is found that the values of α_n for the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes lie in the range 0.78-0.98 in the presence of uni- and poly-valent cations and anions at their concentrations just sufficient to suppress the maxima. An attempt to estimate, n_a , the number of electrons involved in the rate-determining step, apparently leads to the conclusion^{11,12} that n_a is equal to 2 because for totally irreversible systems, as the present ones are, ' α ' should be less than¹⁴ 0.5. However, according to Meites^{5(a)} only a single electron can be transferred at a time during the course of electrode reaction, and a value of n_a exceeding 1 should merely mean that the successive steps are too nearly simultaneous to be distinguished on the time scale implicit in the polarographic measurements.

From a separate study¹⁵ concerned with $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plots in respect of polarographic reduction of chloronitrobenzenes, it was concluded that the number of H^+ ions involved in the rate-determining step is 1. Having thus established the stoichiometry of the rate-determining step, i.e., $n_a=2$ and $H^+=1$, the following mechanism can be suggested for the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloronitrobenzenes at pH 7.09 :

References

1. S. S. SHAKYA, K. CHANDRA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1982, 21A, 411.
2. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
3. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323.
4. J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZECK, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 836.
5. L. MIETES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965. (a) 241, (b) 227, (c) 323, (d) 246.
6. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p. 437.
7. M. SINGH, G. RAM and S. K. JHA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 406.
8. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4944.
9. P. KIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4148.

SHAKYA, CHANDRA & SINGH : STUDIES ON THE SUPPRESSION OF POLAROGRAPHIC MAXIMA ETC.

10. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", Interscience Publ., New York, 1952, Vol. I, p. 166.
11. S. K. VIJAYAKSHAMMA and R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1969, **23**, 99.
12. S. L. GUPTA and N. KISHORE, *Indian J. Chem.* 1971, **9**, 236.
13. KRISHNA, A. VARSHNEY, M. C. DUBEY and S. K. JHA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 658.
14. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr., Prague*, 1951, **1**, 69.
15. RAM RATAN and M. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).